

Narratives Of Master Teachers In English In A Remote Public School

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Abstract

Master teachers in English played a pivotal role in shaping language education, navigating both challenges and opportunities that influenced their professional and personal experiences. This qualitative study employing transcendental phenomenology approach explored the lived experiences of master teachers in English in remote public schools at Lake Sebu, under the Division of South Cotabato. Data were collected through in-depth interviews and thematic analysis was applied to systematically process and interpret the gathered information. Thematic analysis revealed various relevant themes which encapsulated the experiences of master teachers such as life-world experiences including bridging cultures through language, cultivating minds, touching hearts, optimizing learning environments, guiding the educator's path, and commitment beyond the classroom; challenges and contexts, namely balancing commitment and

life, the burden of the profession, teaching against the odds, breaking barriers in learning, strengthening ties, strengthening education, keeping the classroom alive, enduring hardships in remote teaching, beyond teaching, a lasting legacy, and passion as the heart of teaching; and future views, comprising empowering future educators, building a stronger education system, growing as leaders and lifelong learners, and transforming classrooms for the future. This study provided a comprehensive understanding of the experiences of master teachers in English, highlighting their dedication, struggles, and aspirations in delivering quality education despite constraints. The findings offered valuable insights for developing policies and programs that support and empower master teachers, ensuring that quality language education reaches even the most geographically isolated communities.

Keywords: experiences, phenomenology, master teachers in English, language education, remote public schools

Introduction

Master teachers in English, especially in remote public schools, shaped students' learning experiences and outcomes. In addition to teaching curriculum material, these teachers mentored and led their educational communities. Master teachers in remote areas faced poor infrastructure, socioeconomic inequities that affected their instruction, a lack of resources, few professional development opportunities, and isolation

from broader professional networks. Nevertheless, in spite of these challenges, they showed creative teaching methods and a great dedication to encouraging student participation and success.

In the Indonesian context, Fadilah et al. (2023) identified systemic concerns such as insufficient teacher quality, low student motivation, and limited parental support, stressing the urgent need for structural reforms in rural education. These issues, although context-specific, reflect broader global challenges that require targeted and sustainable interventions to enhance the capacity of educators and ensure equitable access to quality education in marginalized communities.

Master teachers in the Philippines frequently have major challenges in providing high-quality English instruction since many of the country's rural and mountainous areas lack adequate facilities and resources (Abasolo et al., 2021). These difficulties included overcrowding in classrooms, restricted access to instructional materials, and insufficient technology (Visayans, 2022). Despite these limits, master teachers displayed perseverance and ingenuity in establishing novel teaching practices adapted to the requirements of their students and communities (Kaya Volunteer, 2022).

This study explored the experiences, challenges, and contributions of master teachers in English in rural public schools by analyzing their narratives. Their insights shaped educational policies promoting equity and excellence in language education, enhancing our understanding of English teaching in public schools.

Theoretical Framework

The perspectives of Connelly and Clandinin (1990), Jean Piaget (1920) Constructivist Learning Theory, Schön (1983) Reflective Practice Theory, and Vygotsky (1978) Social Constructivism Theory were all applied to this study. A qualitative research methodology known as "narrative inquiry" places a strong emphasis on the value of individual experiences and tales in explaining societal processes and human behavior. According to this idea, people create meaning by reflecting their identities, values, and beliefs in the narratives they tell (Connelly and Clandinin, 1990). Using narrative inquiry, researcher may examine how master teachers at isolated public schools around Lake Sebu perceive their experiences and the difficulties they encountered in the classroom. The personal narratives of master teachers gathered and analyzed for this project used narrative inquiry.

The research provided insights into participants' coping mechanisms, educational methods, and the influenced of their narratives on their professional development through in-depth interviews and participant sharing. This strategy assisted in placing the teachers' experiences into the larger framework of education, emphasizing the particular difficulties and triumphs that distant educators face (Webster and Mertova, 2007).

Constructivist learning theory held that experiences and social interactions shaped knowledge construction. Its foundations were in the theories of Piaget and Vygotsky. According to this approach, students must actively interact with their surroundings to developed comprehension (Fosnot, 2005). According to this idea, master teachers' teaching methods were influenced by their contacts with students, peers, and the community as well as by their reflections on these encounters.

Through the use of constructivist concepts, the research examined how master teachers used their narratives to develop their identities and educational techniques. The study demonstrated how teaching and learning

in distant public schools were collaborative by looking at the social environments in which these teachers worked. According to Griffiths and Macleod (2008), this approach shed light on how master teachers modified their methods in response to their interactions and reflections, which eventually aided in their professional development.

Schön (1983) developed the reflective practice theory, which highlighted the value of introspection in professional growth. It entailed evaluating past experiences critically to advance practice in the future. Reflective practice helped expert educators gained a deeper understanding of their teaching methods and how well they work in various classroom environments. The research employed reflective practice as a framework to examine the accounts of experienced educators. The research identified how reflection influenced participants' decision-making and improved their effectiveness as teachers by encouraging them to reflect on their experiences and methods. This strategy emphasized how reflection helped teachers in rural public schools became more resilient and adaptable (Richardson, 2000).

Social Constructivism Theory, drawn on Vygotsky's ideas, stressed the significance of social interactions in the production of knowledge. According to Vygotsky (1978), learning was a collaborative process that was impacted by environmental and cultural variables. This idea emphasized the significance of community and cooperation in forming educational practices within the framework of master teachers. Through the application of social constructivism, the study investigated how master teachers at remote public schools interacted with their communities and worked together with other educators to improved their methods of instruction. The research demonstrated how social interactions and cultural environments impacted these educators' teaching practices and support their professional growth by examining their narratives (Rosiek and Atkinson, 2005).

Research Question

To better understand how master teachers modified their pedagogies, overcome challenges, and encouraged student involvement in rural public schools in the Municipality of Lake Sebu, Division of South Cotabato, this study examined the essential elements of their narratives. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the life-world experiences of master teachers teaching English to students in remote public school?
2. What are contexts of the life-world experiences of master teachers in remote public school?
3. How do master teachers in remote public school view themselves in the future?

Methodology

The research design was Transcendental Phenomenology. By concentrating on comprehending the core of participants' lived experiences, this method enabled researcher to fully capture the complexity and depth of master teachers' narratives within their particular teaching environments. In order to grasp the intricacies of teaching English in remote areas, transcendental phenomenology stressed the significance of bracketing researchers' expectations in order to access the essence of participants' experiences (Moustakas, 1994).

Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in remote public schools in the Municipality of Lake Sebu. This study was carried out for several reasons that address the particular difficulties that educators in this area encounter. First, master teachers in Lake Sebu's remote public schools frequently face major challenges, such as restricted access to resources, poor infrastructure, and socioeconomic issues that can affect their ability to effectively teach (Zamora, 2023).

This was especially crucial in distant locations, where culturally sustaining pedagogies encouraged learners' involvement and sense of belonging (Peristeris, 2017). The study aided in the creation of culturally sensitive teaching methods that respected and represented the distinct identities of Lake Sebu students by recording these stories.

Participants of the Study

Seven Master Teachers currently teaching English in public schools located in the Municipality of Lake Sebu were recognized and extended an invitation to partake in the research. The participants were chosen based on the following inclusion criteria: a) Master Teacher teaching English; b) Participants must have at least three years of teaching experience in remote public schools within the Municipality of Lake Sebu; c) Master Teachers who actively engaged with the local community and incorporated local culture into their teaching will be prioritized; d) Male or Female; e) Participants are willing to share their personal narratives and reflections regarding their teaching experiences. In addition, the study also utilized two debriefers to validate the result, and three validators to validate the interview questions.

Sampling Technique

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants who possessed specific characteristics relevant to the research objectives. This method was particularly effective in qualitative research because it enabled the researcher to concentrate on people who have substantial experience and expertise teaching English in remote public schools. To collect rich, in-depth narratives that captured the complexity of their teaching experiences, the study focused on master teachers who had proven to be effective pedagogues and who had been actively involved in their positions for at least three years (Palinkas et al., 2013; Suri, 2011).

Research Instrument

A semi-structured interview questionnaire was used by the researcher. According to Barclay (2018), the interview's flexible structure allowed the researcher to encourage or prod the respondent if they want more information or if their remarks were interesting. This approach gave the researcher the freedom to ask follow-up questions to elicit additional specific information or to choose an alternative course of action based on the interviewee's statements. Informants were given the freedom to express their opinions in their own words during semi-structured interviews.

Data Gathering Procedure

Master teachers with substantial experience teaching English in remote public schools in the Municipality of Lake Sebu were chosen through the use of a purposive sampling technique. Participants were chosen based on their qualifications, willingness to share their experiences, and teaching experience (at least three years). To guarantee a wide range of experiences and viewpoints, a sample size of seven master teachers were sought (Moustakas, 1994).

All participants were provided with their informed consent before data was collected. Participants got comprehensive information about the goals, methods, and rights of the study, including the freedom to discontinue participation at any moment without facing repercussions. For ethical standards to be maintained throughout the research process, this step was essential.

Semi-structured interviews were used to gather data. This provided participants the opportunity to tell their narratives in their own words while also giving the researcher the freedom to delve into particular topics that come up throughout the discussions.

To extract comprehensive accounts from participants, an interview guide was created that includes open-ended questions. Their teaching experiences, difficulties encountered, methods used, and the effect of their instruction on students were all included in the questions. To promote a more thorough examination of participants' experiences, the guide was adaptable, enabling follow-up questions and suggestions based on their answers.

Data Analysis Method

Thematic analysis, a popular qualitative analysis technique, enabled the discovery and interpretation of patterns and themes within qualitative data, and serve as the foundation for the data analysis method used in this study. The researcher examined the rich narratives offered by master teachers, concentrating on their lived experiences, difficulties, and methods for teaching English in remote locations, through thematic analysis, which was especially appropriate for this study (Moustakas, 1994). Data familiarization, coding, theme building, and interpretation were all steps in the methodical process that guided the study. The researcher transcribed the interviews verbatim and thoroughly reviewed the transcripts to fully understand the data. Using Braun and Clarke's (2006) method, key statements were coded and grouped into meaningful units. These codes were then organized into broader themes that reflected common narratives, providing deeper insight into the challenges of teaching English in remote public schools.

Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the study's results and deliberated the implications of data gathered through an interview guide questionnaire during the interview conducted with the participants.

Relevant Theme 1: Bridging Cultures Through Language

The relevant theme Bridging Cultures Through Language emphasized the essential role of language in promoting inclusive and effective learning, especially in multilingual, remote public-school settings. It comprised two clustered themes: Multilingual Teaching and Cultural Adaptation and Student Empowerment and Language Impact. Language was viewed not only as a means of communication but also as a channel for cultural integration. Burkette (2015) and Ozturk (2024) stressed the importance of embedding cultural contexts in language instruction, enhancing both communication and learning. Jiang et al. (2020) supported this by highlighting that culturally meaningful approaches increase student engagement and foster a sense of belonging.

The second cluster, Student Empowerment and Language Impact, focused on how language mastery transforms students' self-identity. Ratni (2024) noted that digital literacies encouraged critical thinking and autonomy, while Kern (2006) emphasized technology's role in widening access to language learning. Language instruction also built students' cultural competence, preparing them to navigate diverse societies.

Hymes and Landar (1968) underscored that language and culture are interdependent, and Ahmed (n.d.) supported embedding critical thinking to improve intercultural skills. Reflective Practice Theory framed this theme by encouraging educators to adapt teaching based on students' cultural backgrounds, ensuring that language instruction remained both inclusive and transformative.

Relevant Theme 2: Cultivating Minds, Touching Hearts

The theme Cultivating Minds, Touching Hearts captured the dual impact of teaching on both students and educators, structured into two clustered themes: Teaching as a Personal and Emotional Journey and Celebrating Student Achievements. Teachers often experienced personal and professional growth through their relationships with students. According to Poom-Valickis et al. (2017), fulfilling psychological needs such as autonomy, competence, and relatedness enhanced motivation and emotional satisfaction among educators. Thahir et al. (2024) affirmed that when students' needs are met, both learners and teachers benefit emotionally. Coughlan et al. (2021) emphasized that reflective practices help improve teachers' emotional well-being and pedagogical approaches. Denmeade (2017) added that teachers guide students through academic and personal transformation, framing them as educational heroes.

The second cluster, Celebrating Student Achievements, emphasized how student success reinforces teachers' dedication and passion. Rouse (2023) highlighted that educators' personal experiences are deeply connected with their teaching identities, and Batty et al. (2019) found that reflecting on students' progress strengthens teachers' commitment to their profession. The Reflective Practice Theory provided a strong foundation for this theme, promoting deep engagement with one's teaching experience to adapt strategies based on student needs (Fisher & Hill, 2017). Ultimately, reflective practice fosters personal growth, emotional resilience, and a stronger teacher-student connection, aligning with the essence of cultivating minds and touching hearts.

Relevant Theme 3: Optimizing Learning Environments

The relevant theme Optimizing Learning Environments emphasized how master teachers create effective and engaging spaces in remote public schools with limited resources. This theme included two clustered themes: Maximizing Resources and Student Engagement and Designing Effective Teaching Materials, developed from challenges like large class sizes and student absenteeism due to poverty. According to Augustsson et al. (2024), teachers utilized social, material, and cultural resources to increase participation. Ghufron (2021) noted the importance of adapting strategies to support absent students. Interactive strategies and formative assessments were highlighted by Johnson et al. (2019) as key to improving outcomes. Sánchez et al. (2019) emphasized inclusive methods to foster belonging and reduce absenteeism. The design of teaching materials depended on strong pedagogical knowledge (Dwiningsih et al., 2019), with Baene et al. (2023) and Navidad (2019) stressing strategic planning and the integration of technology to address resource gaps. Effective teaching also required understanding students' development (Ghufron, 2021). Reflective Practice Theory supported this theme, promoting ongoing self-assessment and strategy refinement to cultivate inclusive and resourceful environments (Dwiningsih et al., 2019).

Relevant Theme 4: Guiding the Educator's Path

The theme Guiding the Educator's Path explored the personal and professional factors that influenced master teachers' careers in remote public schools. Two clustered themes emerged: Family and External Influences on Teaching and Professional Growth and Innovation. Family played a crucial role in career

motivation, especially in remote areas where emotional support helps teachers overcome systemic challenges (Dung et al., 2020). Despite long and difficult travel to schools, teachers demonstrated resilience, supported by their families. Puspasari et al. (2023) illustrated that during the COVID-19 pandemic, educators adapted to limited resources, reinforcing the importance of endurance in such settings.

Professional development and innovation were equally vital for navigating teaching challenges. Liu et al. (2019) stressed the need for updated pedagogical strategies, while Gustavsson et al. (2019) supported collaborative learning to enhance teaching practices. Teachers in under-resourced areas adapted by integrating technology and innovating classroom methods (Dung et al., 2020; Baimukhambetova, 2024). These efforts improved student engagement and learning experiences. Reflective Practice Theory aligned with this theme, encouraging teachers to analyze personal and external influences, refine their strategies, and enhance both professional growth and student outcomes (Dwiningsih et al., 2019).

Relevant Theme 5: Commitment Beyond the Classroom

The relevant theme Commitment Beyond the Classroom underscored the profound dedication of master teachers in remote public schools, capturing their heavy workloads, leadership roles, and enduring passion for teaching through three clustered themes: Teacher Responsibilities and Well-Being, Leadership and Commitment in Education, and Passion and Dedication in Teaching. Despite risks of burnout, those who engaged in professional development showed increased resilience and job satisfaction (Dewi et al., 2024). Their leadership extended beyond teaching, shaping school policies and mentoring peers (Wenner & Campbell, 2016), while their passion enhanced student engagement (Quines & Ogal, 2023; Pant, 2020). Emotional regulation was essential in challenging contexts (Liu et al., 2023), and Reflective Practice Theory (Dwiningsih et al., 2019) supported continuous self-evaluation and adaptation—affirming teaching as a dynamic, purpose-driven vocation.

Relevant Theme 6: Balancing Commitment and Life

The theme Balancing Commitment and Life captured the challenges faced by master teachers in remote public schools as they managed professional duties alongside personal responsibilities, encompassing the clustered themes Between Duty and Home and The Emotional Toll of Teaching. Educators often struggled with heavy workloads that strained their work-life balance, risking burnout and impacting family interactions (Azeem & Akhtar, 2014), highlighting the need for institutional support. Emotionally, teaching in remote areas contributed to stress and fatigue, affecting job satisfaction (Phelan & Janzen, 2021; Munda & Gache, 2024). Encouragement from peers and strong collegial relationships were vital to fostering resilience (Aras et al., 2022). Guided by Constructivist Learning Theory, teachers continuously shaped and adapted their understanding of work-life balance through lived experiences, reinforcing their personal and professional growth (Black & Halstead, 2021).

Relevant Theme 7: The Burden of the Profession

The Burden of the Profession explores the physical, emotional, and financial challenges faced by master teachers in remote public schools, which were categorized into two themes: The Weight of the Work and The Hidden Costs of Teaching. Teachers often experience physical exhaustion due to high stress and workload, which negatively impacts their health and teaching effectiveness (Xue et al., 2023; Pearn et al., 2024). Emotional tolls, exacerbated by insufficient mental health support, also contribute to burnout,

increasing turnover rates (Collie, 2021; Taysum & Hysa, 2023). Financial struggles, including low pay, further demoralize educators and discourage others from joining the profession, perpetuating shortages (Al'Abri et al., 2023; Chisholm-Burns et al., 2019). Despite these burdens, teachers remain dedicated, emphasizing the need for systemic solutions, such as mental health resources, teacher training, and equitable compensation (Pearn et al., 2024; Karim et al., 2021). Reflective Practice Theory highlights the value of self-reflection in managing these challenges, promoting resilience and well-being (Yuzkiv et al., 2022).

Relevant Theme 8: Teaching Against the Odds

Teaching Against the Odds highlights the resilience and adaptability of master teachers in remote public schools, who face challenges such as limited resources and difficult teaching conditions. This theme was divided into two clusters: Teaching on a Tight Budget and Resourcefulness at Its Best, which underscored the lack of teaching materials, the need for digital tools, and teachers' innovative approaches in remote teaching. Teachers in rural contexts developed creative strategies to continue providing quality education despite logistical challenges, often engaging families and communities to support learning (Kouhia et al., 2021). The shift to online education during the COVID-19 pandemic further highlighted the need for digital resources, with teachers overcoming disparities in technology access by leveraging available tools (Lee, 2024; Schotgues, 2022). Despite limited resources and support, educators demonstrated remarkable adaptability, achieving positive outcomes through their commitment to student success (Garcia et al., 2022; Bugge & Siddiq, 2021). Constructivist Learning Theory, which emphasizes learning through experiences and interactions, serves as a foundation for understanding how teachers facilitated learning in these challenging conditions (Black & Halstead, 2021).

Relevant Theme 9: Breaking Barriers in Learning

Breaking Barriers in Learning explores the innovative strategies master teachers in remote public schools used to address learning gaps, focusing on language barriers, multilingual dynamics, and effective teaching methods. The theme was structured around two key clusters: Language Gaps in Learning and Strategies That Stick. Teachers in linguistically diverse classrooms adapted their methods to overcome language barriers, utilizing strategies like code-switching to bridge communication gaps (Saadati et al., 2021; Brown et al., 2022). Emphasizing the need for technology and culturally contextualized teaching, educators tailored their approaches to meet varied language needs, enhancing engagement (Ewing & Cooper, 2021; Fidan, 2021). Storytelling, highlighted by Zhang (2020), became a key tool in connecting students to the material and fostering comprehension. Additionally, adaptive learning models, as discussed by Sutardi et al. (2021), equipped teachers with the skills to address challenges in remote teaching. Social Constructivism Theory (Vygotsky, 1978) underpinned these efforts, stressing the role of social interactions and cultural contexts in fostering meaningful learning experiences.

Relevant Theme 10: Strengthening Ties, Strengthening Education

Strengthening Ties, Strengthening Education underscores the critical role of community collaboration in improving educational outcomes in remote public schools, structured around two clusters: Bridging the Home-School Gap and Schools and Villages Together. Eden et al. (2024) emphasized the importance of parental and community involvement in fostering student success, noting that limited parental support often results from socioeconomic barriers. The second cluster, Schools and Villages Together, highlights how community engagement can enhance educational quality by creating partnerships that address both academic and social needs (Godfrey, 2016; Chzhen et al., 2022). Local communities also contribute to overcoming educational barriers through innovative projects and resource-sharing initiatives, such as nutrition education programs that integrate community support (Hampden-Thompson et al., 2015; Bello &

Pillay, 2019). Social Constructivism Theory (Black & Halstead, 2021) supports this theme by emphasizing the role of social interactions and community contexts in knowledge construction, demonstrating that collaboration between parents, teachers, and communities enhances student learning and creates relevant, meaningful educational experiences.

Relevant Theme 11: Keeping the Classroom Alive

Keeping the Classroom Alive highlights, the commitment of master teachers in remote public schools to maintaining student engagement and motivation despite significant challenges. This theme focuses on strategies like fostering social belonging, as Mikami et al. (2017) found that students who feel connected to their peers and teachers engage more deeply and achieve academically. Self-regulated learning (SRL) also plays a crucial role, as Dewi and Hadiana (2021) noted that students who manage their goals and time effectively are more engaged, especially in remote learning. Barriers to engagement, such as socioeconomic status and academic burnout, contribute to absenteeism and disengagement, with students from low-income families often facing unreliable internet access and inadequate learning environments (Tomaszewski et al., 2020; Arlinkasari et al., 2017; Niyibizi, 2024). Studies show that engaging curricula and teacher interaction are vital for sustaining motivation (Li et al., 2021; Lam et al., 2015). Social constructivism theory (Vygotsky, 1978) supports these efforts by emphasizing the importance of social interaction and community in fostering motivation and engagement, highlighting the teacher's role in facilitating collaborative learning.

Relevant Theme 12: Enduring Hardships in Remote Teaching

Enduring Hardships in Remote Teaching captures the multifaceted struggles faced by master teachers in remote public schools, categorized into two themes: The Hard Road to Teaching and Crumbling Classrooms, Enduring Lessons. Teachers endure significant physical and emotional challenges, including long journeys to isolated schools, loneliness, and a lack of support networks, compounded by inadequate infrastructure such as unreliable internet access (Gershy & Katz, 2023) and insufficient resources (Baraquia, 2020). Additionally, poor physical learning environments contribute to emotional exhaustion and burnout, negatively affecting both teacher effectiveness and student engagement (Collie, 2021; Kamboj & Garg, 2021). The literature emphasizes the importance of infrastructure, teacher resilience, and collaboration between teachers, students, and parents in mitigating these challenges (Ewing & Cooper, 2021; Harris & Jones, 2020). Reflective practice theory (Schön, 1983) is particularly relevant, as it highlights how self-reflection and adaptation help teachers navigate these hardships, ultimately improving their instructional effectiveness, emotional well-being, and ability to engage students in challenging environments.

Relevant Theme 13: Beyond Teaching, A Lasting Legacy

Beyond Teaching, A Lasting Legacy underscored the multifaceted contributions of master teachers in remote public schools, emphasizing their roles as mentors, community leaders, and resilient educators across three clustered themes: More Than Just a Teacher, Small Wins, Big Impact, and Beyond the Lesson Plan. These educators built strong emotional connections that enhanced motivation, resilience, and student well-being, particularly in isolated learning environments (Ewing & Cooper, 2021; Zik, 2024). Celebrating small victories reinforced self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation, fostering optimism and perseverance amid challenges (Yang et al., 2018; Pak et al., 2020). Their holistic teaching approach integrated real-world applications and community-based projects, promoting experiential learning and contextual understanding

(Alfi & Amalia, 2024; Coker, 2021; Burke et al., 2023). Through these practices, master teachers disrupted systemic disadvantages, promoted equity, and created psychologically safe spaces conducive to risk-taking and growth (Yang et al., 2018; Zik, 2024; Coker, 2021). Grounded in constructivist learning theory, which views learning as an active, experience-driven process (Bruner, 1966; Piaget, 1973), their legacy lies in fostering independent, critical thinkers and lifelong learners equipped to navigate real-world challenges.

Relevant Theme 14: Passion as the Heart of Teaching

Passion as the Heart of Teaching underscored the essential role of passion in driving master teachers in remote public schools, highlighting how their dedication created supportive learning environments and lasting impacts beyond academics, as captured in the themes *The Price of Passion* and *A Calling, Not Just a Career*. Despite limited resources and difficult conditions, these educators made significant sacrifices—such as extended hours and emotional investment—demonstrating unwavering commitment that enhanced student engagement and outcomes (Serin, 2023). Their passion was not just professional but deeply personal, serving as a source of hope and inspiration for students facing adversity, and reinforcing the belief that teaching is a vocation rooted in fulfillment and purpose (Wang, 2022). Literature affirmed that passionate educators not only experience higher job satisfaction and efficacy but also cultivate dynamic, nurturing classrooms that boost student motivation and learning (Serin, 2023; Wang, 2022; Allen et al., 2015; Jimerson & Haddock, 2015). Aligned with constructivist learning theory, which views learning as an active, contextual, and socially-driven process (Bruner, 1966; Piaget, 1973), these teachers inspired meaningful learning by connecting content to students' lives and fostering lifelong growth.

Relevant Theme 15: Building Future Careers

Building Future Careers highlighted the proactive role of master teachers in remote public schools in mentoring, training, and supporting future educators to ensure a sustainable educational ecosystem, as captured in the clustered themes *Guiding Future Teachers* and *Training and Supporting Teachers*. Through mentorship, seasoned educators helped novice teachers develop professional identity, confidence, and instructional competence, which improved retention and classroom effectiveness, especially in isolated settings (Ernest et al., 2013; Al-Rawashdeh et al., 2023; Sin, 2020). Master teachers also led professional development workshops and fostered collaborative learning frameworks that supported innovation and built strong professional learning communities (Quinn et al., 2020; Muijs, 2015). Literature supported mentorship and experiential training as crucial for bridging theory and practice, enhancing teacher efficacy, and improving student outcomes (Ernest et al., 2013; Al-Rawashdeh et al., 2023; Sin, 2020). School-university partnerships and tailored PD initiatives further reinforced teacher preparedness and instructional quality (Quinn et al., 2020), while professional learning networks enabled reflective teaching and collaborative planning (Muijs, 2015). Grounded in social constructivism theory (Vygotsky, 1978), this theme emphasized that learning occurs through interaction and shared experiences, with master teachers acting as facilitators of growth—cultivating a culture of collaboration, resilience, and continuous professional innovation.

Relevant Theme 16: Building a Stronger Education System

Building a Stronger Education System emphasized the critical role of master teachers in remote public schools in shaping and transforming education through two clustered themes: *Improving Education Policies* and *Creating Lasting Educational Programs*. Master teachers, drawing from firsthand classroom

experiences, contributed valuable insights to policy-making, ensuring that frameworks are responsive to the unique needs of remote schools and promote equity and teacher professionalism (Nuraeni et al., 2023). They also designed and implemented sustainable, culturally responsive programs that recognized diverse student backgrounds, increased engagement, and improved academic outcomes (Karataş & Oral, 2015). Long-term educational improvements were supported through inclusive teacher training and professional development, which fostered teaching efficacy and addressed diverse learning needs (Karataş & Oral, 2015; Dericioğlu & Öznaçar, 2024). Literature affirmed that teacher involvement in policymaking and culturally aware pedagogy enhanced educational standards and learning environments (Giannakos et al., 2021). Moreover, the integration of technology in education and targeted STEM training initiatives improved access and student achievement, particularly in remote areas (Giannakos et al., 2021). Grounded in social constructivism (Vygotsky, 1978), this theme highlighted how knowledge is built through collaboration, with master teachers acting as both learning facilitators and key contributors to policy and program development, thereby strengthening education systems for future generations.

Relevant Theme 17: Growing as Leaders and Lifelong Learners

Growing as Leaders and Lifelong Learners captured the commitment of master teachers in remote public schools to enhance their skills and leadership capacities while promoting a culture of continuous learning through two clustered themes: Growing and Learning for Life and Leading with Purpose. Master teachers recognized lifelong learning as essential, engaging in ongoing professional development, reflective practices, and participation in learning communities to refine teaching methods and inspire innovation (Sun, 2022; Impedovo, 2016). This commitment not only benefitted their own growth but also fostered adaptability, resilience, and a growth mindset among students. As proactive leaders, master teachers influenced educational practices and policies, mentored peers, and advocated for culturally responsive teaching to create inclusive learning environments (Impedovo, 2016). Research supported the importance of reflection, professional collaboration, and teacher leadership in driving educational improvement (Sun, 2022; Impedovo, 2016). Reflective Practice Theory (Schön, 1983) underpinned this theme, emphasizing how continuous self-evaluation enables educators to adapt strategies, enhance leadership, and make meaningful contributions to teaching and learning.

Relevant Theme 18: Transforming Classrooms for the Future

Transforming Classrooms for the Future emphasized the vital role of master teachers in remote public schools in fostering innovative and inclusive learning environments through two clustered themes: Bringing Technology into Teaching and Making Learning Inclusive and Student-Focused. Master teachers used digital tools to design interactive, personalized instruction that enhanced engagement and learning outcomes, while also addressing the digital divide through ongoing professional development (Ahmed, 2024; Anyolo et al., 2018). Despite infrastructure challenges, technology enabled dynamic teaching and bridged access gaps. Simultaneously, inclusive education practices that embraced cultural diversity and student-centered strategies, such as differentiated instruction and collaborative learning, empowered students and promoted equity in the classroom (Anyolo et al., 2018; Brodie & Jackson, 2024). Research supported the role of educators in integrating technology and inclusive teaching to enrich learning and better prepare students for future challenges (Ahmed, 2024; Brodie & Jackson, 2024). Grounded in Social Constructivism (Vygotsky, 1978), this theme highlighted how collaborative, technology-integrated, and inclusive approaches fostered community, active participation, and meaningful learning for all students.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were based on the synthesized relevant themes and the participants' experiences.

Master teachers in English in remote public schools played a multifaceted and indispensable role in shaping education. Their profession extends beyond classroom instruction, encompassing mentorship, leadership, and community-building. They served as bridges between cultures, facilitators of language development, and advocates for student-centered learning despite the challenging conditions they face. Their experiences were a deep commitment to fostering academic growth, instilling values, and optimizing learning environments to ensure their students receive quality education.

Despite their dedication, master teachers grapple with significant challenges that test their resilience and adaptability. They constantly balanced personal and professional responsibilities, navigated resource limitations, and overcame barriers to student engagement. Teaching in remote schools often means enduring difficult working conditions, geographical isolation, and systemic constraints that impact their ability to innovate and sustain high-quality instruction. However, their passion for education remained steadfast, driving them to seek creative solutions, strengthen collaboration, and cultivate meaningful relationships with students and colleagues.

The master teachers held an optimistic vision for the future of education. They see themselves as agents of change, committed to empowering future educators, strengthening the education system, fostering leadership, and transforming learning environments. They recognized the importance of lifelong learning, policy advocacy, and the integration of modern teaching strategies to make education more inclusive, engaging, and effective.

All things considered, the findings emphasized that master teachers in English were vital pillars of education in remote communities. Their experiences call for greater institutional support, professional development opportunities, and policy interventions that will enhance their teaching capacities and sustain their invaluable contributions. Their narratives underscored the need for a holistic approach to educational reform—one that values, supports, and empowers educators as they continue to shape future generations.

Recommendation

The following were recommended based on the findings and conclusions:

1. Master Teachers may participate in reflective practice, peer mentoring, and leadership training to refine teaching approaches. They can advocate for institutional support, funding, and infrastructure improvements while contributing to curriculum development and policy discussions for remote schools.
2. School Administrators may prioritize teacher support programs, training workshops, and resource-sharing initiatives. Address teacher well-being through workload management, incentives, and mental health programs, while improving infrastructure and technology integration in schools.
3. DepEd-Policymakers may develop targeted interventions for remote teaching challenges, including resource allocation, digital learning access, and mentorship programs. Conduct regular assessments to ensure effective policy implementation tailored to rural school needs.
4. Future Researchers may expand research on master teachers' long-term impact, technology in education, and professional development programs. Incorporate quantitative and qualitative data for a more comprehensive analysis of interventions in remote schools.

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